

A NEW COLORIMETRIC METHOD FOR THE CHLORATE ION.

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A new colorimetric method by using pyridine in concentrated H_2SO_4 , producing permanent violet colour with chlorates, has been described for detection and rough estimation of small amounts of chlorates.

Only a few colorimetric methods are available for the detection of the chlorate ion. Virgilli (*Ann. chim. anal. chim. appl.*, 1909, **14**, 85) suggested the use of aniline hydrochloride for detecting chlorates. A solution of aniline hydrochloride in hydrochloric acid at once develops a violet colour with chlorates, but it is not permanent and changes to blue. The method was improved by Jones (*Analyst*, 1931, **56**, 807). The test, however, is not specific for chlorate ions and cannot be applied in presence of other oxidising substances which also give the same colouration. Poch (*Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1922, **20**, 662) reported a qualitative test for chlorate. The method depends upon the oxidation of ammonium thiocyanate by chlorate in specially prepared test paper with the production of a pale lemon-yellow to cadmium-yellow mixture of oxidation products of sulphocyanic acid. Offord (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1935, **7**, 93) used this method for quantitative estimation of small amounts of chlorate in plant extracts. Halogens, bromate, iodate, persulphate, peroxide, and cupric salts, however, colour the thiocyanate test-paper similarly as chlorate.

The method described in the present paper was devised mainly for detecting small amounts of chlorate in presence of chloride. The method is based on the fact that a solution of pyridine in sulphuric acid produces a permanent violet colouration with chlorate. The test is best carried out as follows: 3 c.c. of pyridine is taken in a test tube and 9 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid are added to it drop by drop with constant shaking. When the liquid has cooled, the reagent is ready for use. If the substance to be examined is in solution, the solution containing chlorate is carefully evaporated to dryness in a small porcelain basin, as the colour is well developed with solid chlorates. A drop or two of the reagent is then added to the solid substance when an intense violet colour is produced which is quite permanent.

The colour produced varies from violet (0.01 to 1 mg. per c.c.) through deep violet (1 to 10 mg. per c.c.) to almost black (10 mg. per c.c. or over). It will be seen that the presence of chloride, bromide, iodide, perchlorate,

nitrate, persulphate, and phosphate does not interfere with the reaction. Coloured substances, such as chromate and dichromate, mask the colour of the chlorate test, and bromate and iodate give a colour similar to that developed by chlorate.

Although the test is mainly qualitative in nature, it may also be applied for quantitative estimation of small amounts of chlorate in absence of interfering substances with a fair degree of accuracy, because the intensity of shade developed is proportional to the quantity of chlorate present. In quantitative work it is advisable to prepare standards for matching the colour of the unknown, by evaporating solutions containing known amounts of potassium chlorate in small porcelain basins, and if the unknown contains a large amount of chlorate it should be dissolved in water and an aliquot part evaporated to dryness.

The method is useful in determining the amount of sodium chlorate in certain weed-killers, in which chlorides are used as diluents of sodium chlorate, sold in the market for the purpose. It is also applicable to the determination of chlorate in mixture with the ingredients of typical nutrient water cultures comprising nitrate, chloride, sulphate and phosphate, because none of these ions interfere with the reaction.

